
Cancer diagnoses with the use of AI

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ABSTRACT

This research will be written to build a model that can be used to determine which AI technology is the most relevant to use during diagnosis. This is the knowledge gap which leads to the following research question: “What is needed to make radiologists start using Artificial Intelligence during a breast cancer diagnosis?”

To answer this question, literature research and expertise interviews were undertaken to design a theoretical model to identify, control, and link the unique characteristics of AI and cancers. This theoretical model will benefit academia and healthcare providers with insight on supporting radiologists about Artificial Intelligence.

Keywords

Artificial Intelligence, Healthcare, Breast Cancer, Diagnosis, Neural networks

INTRODUCTION

Background

Technological innovation diffuses more and more in our economy. These innovations lead to a changing world whereby technology is central. In some cases, technology can also be life-saving, such as the use of technology in healthcare. For instance, the possibility to predict whether a patient has a high risk of getting cancer by the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI). According to the World Health Organization, cancer is the cause of death for 9.6 million people in 2018. Hereby, breast cancer is one of the most common cancers with a death rate of 0.627 million people (World Health Organization, 2018)

Some studies have shown that some AI methods are already implemented in healthcare. The article “Artificial intelligence in healthcare: past, present, and future”, describes the disease areas that use Artificial Intelligence tools include cancer, neurology, and cardiology (Jiang, 2017). One of these methods, the Neural Network, will be used as a case study in order to get a clear view of the requirements of using AI.

The pre-research has shown that breast cancer is a serious threat to health among women. And we have also found that implementing AI within healthcare is possible. So why is artificial intelligence not used massively within healthcare? This is where the knowledge gap exists.

Due the fact that breast cancer is the most curable cancer types if it can be diagnosed early, this research will only focus on breast cancer and will be written in order to obtain more insight to answer the research question: “*What is needed to make radiologists start using Artificial Intelligence during a breast cancer diagnosis?*” (Akay, 2009).

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. The next section will tell more about the method of this research. Section 3 analyzes the interview and the breast cancer case study. This paper will end with a conclusion.

METHODS

In order to answer the above-mentioned research question, we have formulated the following sub-questions:

Table 1. Theoretical sub-questions

SQ1	Why isn't AI massively implemented and what are the challenges AI is facing?
SQ2	What are the challenges AI is facing?
SQ3	How will the future be shaped of radiology?
SQ4	What are the possibilities with AI?

Hypothesis

Before an interview was held, a hypothesis about the subject can be defined. As this paper will investigate what the needs are for radiologists to use artificial intelligence during breast cancer diagnosis, it is assumed that there is a correlation between not using artificial intelligence because of the potential challenges that radiologists are facing.

The assumption is tested and confirmed by research (Castillo, 2013). Below, the following hypothesis can be defined as:

Table 2. Hypothesis

*	Definition
H0	The potential challenges radiologists are facing, does not affect their use of Artificial Intelligence during a diagnosis.
H1	The potential challenges radiologists are facing affects their use of Artificial Intelligence during a diagnosis.

Conceptual Model

The hypotheses are used to visualize the conceptual model by reflecting the potential correlation:

Figure 1. Conceptual model

The straight lines were used to explain the relationship in which the hypothesis is being tested. Three independent variables may affect the dependent variable of using Artificial Intelligence.

Interview

After formulating theoretical sub-question, an interview with a teacher of Tilburg University has been held in order to obtain the overall impression of the current challenges of implementing AI on a large scale within healthcare. The subject of the interview was disclosed a week before the actual meeting, so the interviewee could prepare. We defined the main topics: "AI in healthcare, challenges of implementing AI, and the behaviour of radiologists". The interview strategy was unstructured (non-directive). During the discussion of these topics, further questions by the interviewers have been asked to go more in-depth. We chose this approach due to our aim was to get an overall view of this topic (exploratory approach).

The data that is collected through this interview is recorded, analyzed, and compared with literature research to design the theoretical model which will be discussed. The outcome of the interview is attached as an appendix.

Literature research

The second method of research is the use of case studies by literature research after a general understanding which has been obtained through the interview. After the interview, many case studies on the use of Artificial Intelligence in healthcare were compared and breast cancer was an important subject to choose from as a case study. Breast cancer is a potential case study to be treated with the use of AI, according to the importance of an early diagnosis, because it is the second-largest cause of cancer deaths among women. It is relevant to investigate whether AI predictions can identify breast cancer in an earlier phase and diagnoses

earlier to reduce the mortality rate. The literature papers were selected according to these criteria: unique characteristics, validity, reliability, significance, amount of cited, and title of academic paper or case study. As a result, relevant case studies have been gathered through Google Scholar, Tilburg University Library, and Worldcat. Furthermore, keywords like “AI AND breast cancer” or “AI challenges AND breast cancer” were used to search for the right case studies and academic papers. The case studies are used to gain insight into how Artificial Intelligence was applied during a diagnosis.

AI TECHNOLOGY

Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be defined as the theory and development of computer systems able to perform undertakings, such as breaking down complex medicinal information. The British mathematician Alan Turing (1950) was one of the founders of present-day software engineering and AI. He characterized intelligent conduct in a computer as the capacity to accomplish human-level execution in intellectual errands, this later got well known as the 'Turing test. After the 1950s, scientists have investigated the potential utilizations of intelligent techniques in each field. Gunn investigated the utilization of AI techniques within a surgery in 1976. During this investigation, Gunn examined the ability to diagnose acute abdominal pain with the use of computer analysis (Ramesh, Kambhampati, Monson, Drew, 2004).

Developing AI programs in order to help the clinician in performing diagnosis, the making of therapeutic decisions and prediction the outcome has a relationship with the development of medical artificial intelligence. These programs have been built to help doctors and nurses in their daily work. This kind of system includes Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), fuzzy expert system and hybrid intelligent systems. These tools will be discussed in depth later in this paper (AN Ramesh, 2004)

Some challenges AI is facing

There are numerous success stories that prove the added value of AI and the need for it (as there is described in the previous paragraph). Healthcare institutes that add AI (cognitive interactions and machine learning) to their traditional processes will be able to improve their effectiveness. However, there are some stumbling blocks and therefore the next sub-research question has come forward to provide an answer to what these ‘stumbling rocks’ are.

Why isn't AI massively implemented and what are

the challenges AI is facing?

The usability of AI depends on the available data. There should be sufficient data of such patients belonging in AI databases to make the correct comparison. Consequently, if there's insufficient information of patients from a specific background, AI will make an inaccurate diagnosis and doctors could misjudge in the event that they aren't experienced enough to remember it as false. Therefore “artificial intelligence will not replace radiologists. Yet, those radiologists who use AI will replace the ones who don't”. A malfunction because of algorithmic bias or an inability to keep up the system can result in the loss of this data. Or on the other hand more regrettable still, it can get under the control of inappropriate people who can utilize this data against the individuals concerned. This happens when the framework isn't appropriately verified against hackers. After discussing the challenges which AI is facing, the major challenge can be determined. In the next paragraph ‘Major challenge’ this subject will be discussed further.

Major challenge

The major challenge for AI, which prevents it from being massively implemented is the current doctors. Although the technical and security challenges of using AI are problematic and cause wrong results, the critical factor of using AI-techniques relies mostly on the education and training part.

According to studies (Stead, 2018), (Bi, Hosny, Schabath, & B., 2019), (Xu, Yang, & Xue, 2019), (Coccia, 2019). Future generations of doctors are expected to have technical skills in making an accurate diagnosis. The results come better and faster to improve the lives of patients. However, a major unresolved issue is adapting all the training programs of the schools of medicine worldwide on how to use different types of AI-techniques to treat their patients. This blocks the technological usage of AI in many healthcare providers. Therefore, it requires a long-term plan of educating and training doctors in order to work comfortably alongside AI-techniques. Which brings us to the next subject, ‘the future’. Taking into account the opposing forces of implementing AI, how will the future with AI be shaped?

The future

To have successfully implemented AI, there will be AI solutions required which will make it possible to move forward with AI. The following sub- research question has been formulated to be able to paint a picture of this.

How will the future be shaped of radiology?

The work of doctors will remain fundamental to illuminate complex issues and managing diagnostic procedures. AI will become an essential part in diagnosing cases and taking over monotonous tasks. Healthcare ought to get acquainted with AI and embrace how it will change the course (Jiang, 2017). According to this future perspective, the possibilities with AI became relevant. Therefore, the next paragraph ‘Impact of AI on radiology’

visualizes these possibilities.

Impact of AI on radiology

AI is still a complex technology. Expertise in building and managing AI solutions at scale is required to get the most out of it. To create the right possibilities, the right tools need to be implemented as processes and management strategies to ensure the right possibilities.

What are the possibilities with AI?

Radiologists are anxious to be protagonists of the artificial intelligence revolution and to deal with all the steps from the development to the application. To reach this scope, they propose that preparing projects ought to be embraced to educate learners and clinical radiologists on the circumstances, constraints, and clinical utilization of artificial intelligence-based frameworks. In actuality, the exactness of information-driven artificial intelligence frameworks relies upon data quality. Without radiology expertise, to anticipate a precise result and thusly an effective interpretation of artificial intelligence frameworks from exploring setting to clinical practice is just unrealistic reasoning. The radiologist's role in this technological revolution is fundamental. Data-driven methodologies require somebody that guarantees the quality of information, particularly

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when supervision is required during the preparing of AI models. Moreover, radiologists' skill in diagnosis, treatment planning, and prognosis, and related issues is the foundation of any effective interpretation of developed solution from research to clinical practice (European Society of Radiology, 2010)

One of the decisive possibilities of implementing AI, lies in breast cancer diagnosis. Therefore, the following case study is dedicated to these possibilities within breast cancer.

CASE STUDY

Breast Cancer

Breast cancer is the second largest cause of cancer

deaths among women. At the same time, it is also among the most curable cancer types if it can be diagnosed early. However, since 1989, the number of women who have died of breast cancer has steadily decreased thanks to early detection and treatment improvements (Anderson, Jatoi, & Devesa, 2006). According to the derived data from SEER, there can be forecasted that in the year 2019 there will be 268,600 estimated new breast cancer cases (National Cancer Institute, 2019). Figure 2 shows the breast cancer cases and deaths between the years 1992 and 2016.

Figure 2. Breast cancer cases and deaths 1992-2016

This figure gives the estimated reductions in the rate of death till 2016. The decreasing deaths are correlated with the use of new technology that became available for use. The decreasing deaths results in a higher survival rate, as seen in the third figure, which is presented below.

Figure 3. Survival rate

The 5-year survival rate tells you what percent of people live at least 5 years after the cancer is found. According to the overall data there can be seen that new technology contributes critically to reducing the death rate.

The added value of AI

A team from MIT's Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence Laboratory (CSAIL) and Massachusetts General Hospital (MGH) has created a new deep-learning model that can predict from a mammogram if a patient is likely to develop breast cancer as much as five years in the future. A mammogram is an X-ray picture of the breast. Doctors use a mammogram to look for early signs of breast cancer (Gordon, 2019)

These mammogram can be used in order to teach AI techniques in detecting cancer. Each AI technique has its own strengths and weaknesses. Neural networks are mainly concerned with learning, fuzzy logic with imprecision and evolutionary computation with search and optimization. These techniques will be described further in detail during the paragraphs below.

Neuro-Fuzzy modeling (NFM) is a data handling methodology that permits ambiguity and hence is particularly suited to medical applications. It captures and uses the concept of fuzziness in a computationally effective manner (AN Ramesh, 2004)

The advantages of the concerning AI technologies can be combined together. During the next paragraphs, two AI models will be discussed more in-depth. With the right combination of these technologies a hybrid intelligent system can be produced, which can work in a complementary manner. Their synergy allows a hybrid system to accommodate common sense, extract knowledge from raw data, use human-like reasoning mechanisms, deal with uncertainty and imprecision, and learn to adapt to a rapidly changing and unknown environment (AN Ramesh, 2004).

The Artificial Neural Networks model

Artificial Neural Networks (From now on will be referred to as ANN) are the answer to making computers more human like and help machines

reason more like humans. ANNs are biologically inspired by computational networks and uses different layers of mathematical processing to understand the data it's given (Chauhan, 2015) In the following figure we can see a basic assumption of a Neural Network;

This is simple enough however there is an approach to enhance the intensity of the Neural Network and increment its accuracy by the expansion of a concealed layer that sits between the input and output layers. In the following figure we can see a neural network with a hidden layer;

The neurons are connected by links, and each link has a numerical weight associated with it. See figure 4 for an example.

Figure 4. Artificial Neural Networks

A neural network 'learns' through repeated adjustments of these weights.

One of the important characters of ANNs is that they can learn from their experience in a training environment. The use of multilayer feedforward Perceptron was restricted by the lack of a suitable learning algorithm until Paul Werbos (1974) a PhD student introduced 'backpropagation' learning (Werbos, 1990)

The Neuro-Fuzzy model

According to the research paper "Artificial Intelligence in Predicting Bladder Cancer Outcome: A Comparison of Neuro-Fuzzy Modeling and Artificial Neural Networks" predicting cancer behavior can be achieved with the use of Artificial Intelligence techniques. The research has been determined that the rules of NFM are transparent, enabling validation from clinical knowledge and the manipulation of input variables to allow exploratory predictions. Therefore, this strategy could be utilized broadly in different areas of medicine (Catto, Linkens, & Abbod, 2003).

The main approach for diagnosis of breast cancer is

biopsy. However, biopsy can lead to patient discomfort, bleeding and infection, which can overload the health care system with additional costs. Therefore the first step during choosing the right AI technology, to indicate the main approach for diagnosing a cancer (Keles, Keles, & Yavuz, 2011)

Several researchers developed an expert system called ‘EX-DBC’ to diagnose breast cancer in an efficient way. This system uses the fuzzy rules. During their research, they used the mass data set from UCI Machine Learning Repository. This informational index can be utilized to anticipate the seriousness (kindhearted or harmful) of a mammographic mass injury from BI-RADS qualities and the patient’s age. The Institute of Radiology of the University Erlangen-Nuremberg has collected data for 516 benign and 445 malignant masses between 2003 and 2006. This data has been used to range the BI-RADS from 1 (definitely benign) to 5 (highly harmful). The other attributes of the mammographic mass data were given in Table 3.

Table 3. Attributes applied in the mammographic mass data

Attribute information	Range
BI-RADS	BI-RADS assessment: 1–5 (ordinal)
Age	Age: patient’s age in years (integer)
Shape	Shape: mass shape: round = 1, oval = 2, lobular = 3, irregular = 4 (nominal)
Margin	Margin: mass margin: circumscribed = 1, microlobulated = 2, obscured = 3, ill-defined = 4, spiculated = 5 (nominal)
Density	Density: mass density high = 1, iso = 2, low = 3, fatcontaining = 4 (ordinal)
Class	Severity: benign = 01 or malignant = 10

A neuro-fuzzy model for Ex-DBC can be found in figure 5.

Figure 5. The neuro-fuzzy model for Ex-DBC

The neuro-fluffy framework has a 3-layer feed-forward engineering that is gotten from a nonexclusive fuzzy perception. The units in this system use t-standards or t-conorms as initiation capacities. The shrouded layer speaks to fuzzy guidelines. Fuzzy sets are encoded as association loads. This perspective on a fuzzy framework shows the information stream inside the framework (information and blunder sign), and its parallel nature. Neuro-fluffy framework as an extraordinary three layered feed-forward neural system where:

- Layer 1: express the input variables that means the pattern tuples,
- Layer 2: The fuzzy rules are expressed by the hidden layer,
- Layer 3: express the output variables which shows the means (one unit for every class),
- Layer 4: the units use t-norms and t-conorms as activation functions
- Layer 5: the fuzzy connection weights

The architecture of models contains 3 layers, which is presented in figure 4. The first layer is shown by the color grey and contains 3 inputs references to the pattern features. The second layer is shown by the color green and contains the 5 fuzzy rules. The last layer is represented in the color blue and represents only 2 output units which is malign and benign. There are also 9 hidden layers which has fuzzy rules by using the attributes BI-RADS, Shape and Margin. These rules are cited from the academic paper:

- “ 1. if BI-RADS is very large and Shape is very large and Margin is very large then Malign;
- 2. if BI-RADS is very large and Shape is very large and Margin is medium then Malign;
- 3. if BI-RADS is very large and Shape is large and Margin is small then Malign;
- 4. if BI-RADS is very large and Shape is large and Margin is medium

then Malign;
5. if BI-RADS is very large and Shape is large
and Margin is very
large then Malign;
6. if BI-RADS is very large and Shape is small
then Malign;
7. if BI-RADS is medium then Benign;
8. if BI-RADS is small then Benign;
9. if BI-RADS is large then Benign.”

With this model, the severity of a mammographic mass injury can be determined. A similar model could be designed for a different type of cancer. For this it is crucial to obtain mass data to determine the right attributes (Keles, Keles, & Yavuz, 2011).

CONCLUSION OF THIS STUDY

According to the findings of this study, the combination with choosing the fitting AI method and the right implementation will make radiologists start using AI for diagnosis. The variable ‘implementation’ is actually a process in itself. The fitting implementation process will differ per situation, but the major challenge will remain that the critical factor of using AI-techniques relies mostly on the education and training of doctors. Stephen Hawking's assertion on this subject is that however clever computers are, they could not think. “AI will not replace radiologists, but radiologists who do not use AI will be replaced by radiologists who do,” he says.

Considering these challenges AI is facing and is unsolved. The future will be shaped based on the implementation of AI. Therefore, on the ability of exploiting the opportunities that AI will offer to radiologists and radiology.

Alan Key;

“The best way to predict the future is to invent it”

APPENDIX 1: INTERVIEW**Interview: Senior information manager within healthcare****1. Why isn't AI massively implemented in Healthcare?**

There are two reasons for not implementing AI in healthcare. Firstly, the adaptation of law and regulation of allowing to use AI takes a long period in which healthcare is not authorized to develop AI solutions. Secondly, cultural anxiety in the healthcare of not trying AI-techniques is a reason to be reckoned with.

2. What is the possible reason that radiologists are afraid to use AI?

There are several examples where radiologists are not using AI, but they are often afraid of not knowing what AI-technology does.

3. Do you have a possible example to further explain your previous answer?

Yes, we currently have a data science project at the Utrecht hospital. We are working on implementing algorithms to prevent incidents for patients. However, we have noticed that end users are scared because they do not know how to use the technology and what the ethics of this technology are if an accident happens.

4. Do you think radiologists are afraid to use AI because of an unfair assigned responsibility?

Yes, I think this may be the main reason for not using AI. They are the first to be held responsible if an accident occurs. Moreover, they do not have full control over the AI equipment. Making a small mistake, such as writing the wrong medicine, can cause a lawsuit for a long period. Therefore, they want to prevent mistakes by not using AI techniques in their process if they do not have full control over the types of equipment.

5. To what extent is the implementation of AI techniques a technical challenge, within the healthcare?

I believe that 10% has a technical challenge when implementing AI techniques and 90% when educating them to feel comfortable when using AI techniques. Developing an AI technique is not a challenge. However, people are more concerned about educating users on new technology in healthcare without breaking the law.

6. Do you think the validity of data is significant enough for radiologists to make decisions?

The validity when it comes to making certain decisions cannot be trusted by AI nor should it take over the decision making of radiologists. However, AI can be used as support to work more efficient if there are many data collected.

7. What other challenges must be taken into account when using AI techniques?

As I already have mentioned, use exclusively AI techniques to work efficiently if there is much data collected from patients. Therefore, healthcare should be careful with collecting and securing data. Furthermore, they should be transparent for what purpose the patients' data has been collected.

8. Is there another types of data needed to use AI techniques more efficient for radiologist?

Yes, general documents of the patients' history are required to use AI techniques more efficient. For example, which medicine does he or she use, is it a repeatable disease, is it genetic or is there a comparable patient document to compare with? These factors play a major role in using AI techniques more efficiently because of the many data you have collected to make accurate decisions.

9. How will the future be shaped of radiology?

The radiologist who does not embrace AI techniques is replaced by the radiologist who does embrace AI techniques. I believe that healthcare needs to take a step forward in developing AI solutions and educating emerging radiologists to work comfortably with AI techniques. As a result, radiologists will work efficiently and make more accurate decisions for their patients, saving time, costs, and life for the patient.

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